

Compression behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber/filler reinforced plastics

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Background : axial compressive strength of UD CFRP

- Current status of tensile vs compressive strength of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced plastics (UD CFRP).

T300 [Fiber ••• Tensile strength 3,530 MPa
 UD CFRP ($V_f = 0.6$) ••• Tensile strength 1,860 MPa ($\approx 3530 \times 0.6$, Rule of mixture)
 Compressive strength 1,470 MPa

T1000 [Fiber ••• Tensile strength 6,370 MPa
 UD CFRP ($V_f = 0.6$) ••• Tensile strength 3,040 MPa ($\approx 6370 \times 0.6$, Rule of mixture)
 Compressive strength 1,570 MPa

- | | | |
|--------|--------|-----------------------|
| Toray | Toray | Nippon Graphite Fiber |
| □ M35J | ○ T300 | △ XN-05 |
| M30G | T300J | XN-10 |
| M30S | T400H | XN-15 |
| M40 | T600S | |
| M40J | T700G | |
| M46J | T700S | |
| M50J | T800H | |
| M55J | T800S | |
| M60J | T1000G | |
| | | ● Toray T800S/2592 |

Lower compressive strength than tensile strength

UD CFRP shows unbalanced mechanical property

Tensile and compressive strength of UD CFRP ¹⁾

1) M. Ueda et. al., Composites Part A, 67 (2014), 96-101.

Background : prediction of axial compressive strength

- Axial compressive stress of a UD CFRP is expressed as ^{2,3)}

$$\sigma_x \approx \frac{\tau_{12}}{(\phi_0 + \gamma_{12})}$$

τ_{12}, γ_{12} : Longitudinal shear stress and strain
 ϕ_0 : Fiber misalignment angle

- Maximum σ_x indicates a compressive strength.

- Longitudinal shear stress-strain relation of a UD CFRP and the determination of compressive strength ⁴⁾

Compressive strength is determined by

- fiber misalignment (ϕ_0)
- shear stress-strain relation ($\tau_{12}-\gamma_{12}$)

2) M.R. Wisnom, Composites, 21, (1990), 403-407.

3) B. Budiansky, N.A. Fleck, J Mech Phys Solids, 41, (1993), 183-211.

4) I.M. Daniel, et. al., Composites Part B, 27, (1996), 543-552.

Background : prediction of axial compressive strength

Compressive strength is determined by

- fiber misalignment and the distribution (mean angle ϕ_0 and the standard deviation Σ)
- shear stress-strain relation (τ_{12} - γ_{12})

Objectives : Toward improved axial compressive strength

What is already clear from previous researches

- Compressive strength could be increased by
improving shear-stress-strain relation without degrading fiber misalignment and distribution.

Objectives

- Improved axial compressive strength of UD CFRP

Contents

- Epoxy matrix was modified by three types of fillers: improving shear-stress-strain relation.
- UD CFRP was fabricated based on prepreg-autoclave molding method.
- Fiber misalignment distribution was measured by X-ray CT imaging: to ensure that the fibers are not misaligned.
- Compression tests were performed, and the compressive strength was evaluated.

Materials and Methods

- Materials

Carbon fiber : MR50R-12M, Mitsubishi Chemical
Epoxy resin : Bisphenol A epoxy resin (130deg cure)
Filler : 1 (Nanoscale filler), 2.0wt%
 2 (Sub-micron scale filler), 1.5wt%
 3 (Nanoscale filler), 0.2wt%

*Weight fraction was the ratio to the epoxy resin.

*Weight fraction of fillers was determined based on the viscosity suitable for prepreg production.

- Prepreg : Thin-ply prepreg technique (t =0.04mm)

⇒ Four types of unidirectional prepreg sheets were fabricated with fiber volume fraction $V_f = 60\%$.

ID	Carbon fiber	Epoxy resin	Filler	Filler content
CFRP	MR50R-12M	Bisphenol A epoxy	None	-
CFRP_1			1	2.0wt%
CFRP_2			2	1.5wt%
CFRP_3			3	0.2wt%

Materials and Methods

- Fabrication technique
Autoclave molding

UD CFRP laminate

Compression test specimen

- Specimen configuration

Rectangular coupon : Overall dimension $140 \times 12 \times 2$ mm
(ASTM D6641) Gage section 12×12.7 mm
End tabs : The same CFRP

- Compression test

Loading type : Combined loading (ASTM D6641)
Loading speed : 1.3 mm/min

Schematic image of compression test jig

Materials and Methods

- Measurement of fiber misalignment distribution
 - A X-ray CT system : TDM1601-II, Yamato Scientific, Japan
 - The fiber misalignment angle was quantitatively calculated using the structure tensor analysis technique ⁶⁾.

[Step 1] Cross-section of UD CFRP photographed using X-ray CT system

[Step 2] Distinguishing carbon fibers from epoxy in the cross-section (threshold processing)

[Step 3] Structure tensor analysis and calculation of misalignment angles

[Step 1]

[Step 2]

6) N, Mikkelsen LP, et. al., Compos Appl Sci Manuf, 149 (2021), 106541

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Results : Fiber misalignment angle distribution

- Fiber misalignment angle of CFRP_1

Fiber alignment was not disturbed by the inclusion of filler.

(Note: The average angle is meaningless because it depends on the angle error of the sample cut-out and the placement of sample in the CT scanner).

(a) Misalignment angle from axial direction (z axis)

(b) In-plane (xz) misalignment

(c) Out-of-plane (yz) misalignment

Distribution of fiber misalignment angle

Results : Failure modes

- Compression stress-stroke

- Failure modes

Kink band failure followed by splitting

CFRP

CFRP_1

CFRP_2

CFRP_3

Results : Compressive strength

- Compressive strength improvement rate relative to CFRP without filler reinforcement.
 - CFRP_1 :4.1%
 - CFRP_2 :11%
 - CFRP_3 :0.9%
- Reinforcement of epoxy resin with fillers improved the compressive strength under conditions where fiber alignment was not degraded.
- The improvement effect varies depending on the type of filler.

Conclusions

- Four types of unidirectional carbon fiber/filler reinforced plastic were fabricated using a prepreg-autoclave molding method.
- Compressive strength was improved by reinforcing the matrix with filler, provided that the fillers did not degrade the fiber alignment and the distribution.
- The effect of fillers on the axial compressive strength varied depending on the filler type.

[Free app for Compressive strength estimation](#)

[Questions and comments](#)

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<https://github.com/Naruki-Ichihara/strong/releases/tag/v0.2.4>